

INFLUENCE OF THE PRINCIPALS' LEADERSHIP STYLES TOWARDS TEACHER'S PERFORMANCE AT LICEO SCHOOLS IN LAGUNA

PSYCHOLOGY AND EDUCATION: A MULTIDISCIPLINARY JOURNAL

Volume: 33

Issue 9

Pages: 1060-1070

Document ID: 2025PEMJ3224

DOI: 10.70838/pemj.330908

Manuscript Accepted: 02-25-2025

Influence of the Principals' Leadership Styles towards Teacher's Performance at Liceo Schools in Laguna

Norlyn S. Letegio,* Elmer C. Escala

For affiliations and correspondence, see the last page.

Abstract

Leadership is an integral part of an institution. This study aimed to determine the influence of the principal's leadership style – transformational and transactional towards teacher's performance in Liceo schools. The respondents of the study were teachers in different Liceo schools in Cluster 2. Results of the study shows that – (1) the majority of the teachers that are employed in the Catholic institution placed importance on their professional growth and as to the years in service, most of the teachers stayed longer in the institution because of they acknowledge the effort of their principal; (2) 56% of the employed teachers got very satisfactory as their evaluation performance; (3) inspirational motivation and contingent reward influenced the performance of the teachers; (4) among the two leadership style, only transformational leadership style showed significant difference to the Cluster 2 schools; (5) respondent's profile – educational attainment and length of service showed no significant difference; (6) transformational and transactional leadership style have direct influence on the teacher's performance in Cluster 2 Liceo schools. The development plan is proposed to increase the teacher's performance in the future.

Keywords: *leadership, transformational leadership, transactional leadership, teacher's performance*

Introduction

Leadership plays a crucial role in teacher performance (Hartinah et al., 2020; Andriani et al., 2018). A good leader creates a positive and supportive environment where teachers can thrive. Good teachers are also good leaders who motivate and inspire their students to achieve their best.

Therefore, a principal's leadership has a direct impact on the performance of their subordinates. (Hartinah et al., 2020; Andriani et al., 2018). A high-performance culture and teachers' full potential are fostered by effective school principals, who use their leadership abilities to improve student outcomes (Hartinah et al., 2020).

Leadership is a prevalent notion that has been continuously examined. The definitions of leadership can be complex, unclear, and even contradictory. While some experts argue that leaders who prioritize individuals are the most prosperous, others assert that the achievements of a leader determine their effectiveness. In terms of school leadership, the quality of the school administrator's leadership may serve as a gauge for the school's success. The school administrator could be a principal, school head, or a designated teacher-in-charge who is accountable for managing a school, (Jamon 2017).

The school principal is a critical figure in achieving the national education goals. They are responsible for setting the school's vision and mission and ensuring that all staff and students work towards achieving these goals (Nurdiansyah, 2021, as cited by Raupu et al., 2021). Rahman & Subiyantoro (2021), as cited by Raupu et al. (2021), posited that the principal is the conductor of the school. They must use all the instruments (finances, personnel, facilities) to create a symphony of learning that benefits all students. However, every principal has a different way of leading. To be successful, principals need to have an effective leadership style (Raupu et al., 2021).

The principal is mainly responsible for assisting the administration in planning, directing, and organizing the various activities. Establishing and maintaining a very good teaching-learning environment for the programs of education is mainly the task of a principal or head of a school. The principal should also help the instructors in their instructional strategies. Principals are needed to accomplish the goals and objectives of an institution. The principal must give the teachers highly valued visions specific to their daily practices at the same time working towards creating the environment that supports outstanding teacher performance (Saleem et al., 2020).

Also, leaders play several roles, such as setting direction and goals for the future, acting as change agents, negotiating, and coaching. Research on leadership is conducted using different methodologies and definitions depending on the researcher (Sunaryo W. et al. 2021). Asbari (2020) as cited by Sunaryo, et. al (2021) revealed that it was that having a leader in an organization is crucial. The leader serves as a mentor and sets the direction for the future, acts as a catalyst for change, negotiates, and provides coaching.

In addition, leadership style is how a leader behaves and influences the people in their organization (Raupu et al., 2021; Wibowo & Hasanah, 2021). It is a complex process in which the leader helps others achieve goals and improve the organization (Raupu et al., 2021; Wirjana & Supardo, 2011).

Furthermore, Ariawan, A. (2020) states that the effectiveness of a leader in enhancing the performance of their team members is mainly contingent on their conduct in executing leadership functions within their strategic approach. The style or behavior of a leader can be discerned from their decision-making process, governance or directive methods, task delegation, communication style, ability to stimulate enthusiasm among subordinates, guidance and direction, discipline enforcement, control and supervision of organizational

members' work, meeting leadership, and methods of reprimanding and imposing sanctions or penalties. Hence, organizations require a leader capable of spearheading change (Ariawan, A. 2020; Abdussamad, 2014). Effective leadership, which focuses not only on power and control but also on welfare, satisfaction, and enhancement of human resource quality, can fulfill its functions and contribute to achieving organizational objectives (Ariawan, A. 2020; Shahab & Nisa, 2014).

On the other hand, "performance" comes from the word "to perform," which means to do something as desired or expected. In the work context, performance refers to the ability to carry out tasks according to responsibility, both in quantity and quality (Kartini et al., 2020; Sinambela, 2018; Tobari, 2015). On the other hand, teacher performance is the teacher's ability to deliver instruction effectively. It involves teachers taking responsibility for their students' learning and ensuring their progress. Teachers must also be serious, responsible, and sincere in their work (Kartini et al., 2020; Kartini & Kristiawan, 2019; Supardi, 2014).

Moreover, teachers' work performance is how well they do their job. It is based on their skills, experience, and dedication Asnawati, Arafat, & Putra (2021). Teachers perform well when they are loyal and committed to teaching, have mastered and developed learning materials, have good teaching discipline, are creative in their teaching, collaborate with other school members, are role models for their students, have a good personality, are honest and objective when guiding students, and take responsibility for their duties Asnawati, Arafat, & Putra (2021). Principals evaluate teacher performance (Asnawati et al., 2021).

Also, one of the most expensive resources in a school is its teachers. Principals understand how important it is to select and keep the greatest candidates. A principal should do his best to ensure that new teachers make some social connections, particularly with positive and influential colleagues. (Whitaker et. al., 2019).

Likewise, Kalsoom et al. (2018) emphasizes the pivotal role leaders play in organizations, aiding employees in reaching their targets and aspirations. They cite Northouse (2007), suggesting that leadership is the capacity of a person to inspire a group towards goal attainment. This process involves an individual engaging with the organization's workforce, motivating them, and assisting them in meeting their objectives (Kalsoom et al., 2018; Chaudhry & Javed, 2012). Leaders are the catalysts that boost employee performance and job satisfaction. Despite the ongoing debates surrounding leadership roles (Kalsoom et al., 2018; Islam et al., 2012), the necessity for a leader in organizations remains undisputed (Kalsoom et al., 2018; Zenger & Folkman, 2002). The performance of a group is primarily influenced by its leader, implying that effective leadership can lead to efficient task execution by the group (Kalsoom et al., 2018; Drucker, 1996).

Furthermore, based on the research conducted by Mohammed Al-Malki and Wang Juan in 2018, leaders are believed to positively influence a company's overall effectiveness by impacting their team members' performance. Team members perceive their leader's role as a highly significant resource. This perception arises from the leaders' pivotal role in shaping group norms and assisting team members in addressing and surmounting challenges within a team environment. Furthermore, the study also emphasizes the importance of leaders providing innovative guidance to support team members in attaining both the team's and the organization's objectives.

In addition, Al-Malki, M. & Juan, W. (2018) and Boyett (2006) studies witnessed that the position of a hierarchy is very important to win the respect of his or her subordinates and ningún their dedication to the end of the project. It explained the influence of a leader as follows. Foremost and the first one is that ideals influence, which means leaders must be charismatic. Ideal influence makes leaders perform confidently and competently. They have to be able to motivate and inspire their subjects. That is more or less their role as role models. How they are capable of approaching each on its own is a key factor in how to handle them. Each person's character traits, requirements, objectives, and attitude towards particular jobs are not the same. Leaders, therefore, have to administer to each team member in a personal way.

Arikewuyo (2009), cited by Umar et al. (2021), said that the key responsibilities of the school principal are assigning tasks to the staff members. In addition, the principals are seen as the school's chief financial officer, responsible for overseeing the school's operation administration and guiding the development of the curriculum and teaching method.

In addition, Onwubiko et al. (2015), cited by Umar, Kenyathulla, & Hoque (2021), concluded that the principal deals with the school's administration in addition to serving in management, community relations, supervision, instructional leadership, curriculum design, and as a catalyst for systemic change in the educational system.

The principal's leadership can significantly impact teacher performance, just as important as teacher performance itself. Leadership is essential in any activity (Ross & Gray, 2006; Ul-Hameed et al., 2019; Suharso et al., 2019). The principal's leadership in education can motivate teachers to improve their performance that may lead to have a school success (Cheng, 1994; Suharso et al., 2019).

Influential school leaders can adapt their leadership style to the situation's needs. It means being able to be democratic, autocratic, laissez-faire, transformational, transactional, or any other style necessary to achieve the desired outcome. Both transactional and transformational types of leadership will be involved in this study.

Transformational leadership aims to encourage and inspire staff members to realize their own skills and work together toward the same goal. This style of leadership comprises developing a future vision in 12 steps, sharing it with the team, and giving everyone on the team the freedom to own their job and contribute to the vision. As cited by Davis (2023), Allen et al. (2015) noticed that the development of a positive work environment can be directly impacted by the characteristics of a transformative leader. Workers who are led by a

transformative leader have some influence over decisions made by the organization, which encourages a strong work ethic. Through empowering team members to understand the importance of their work, transformational leaders inspire and motivate others.

Furthermore, transformational leaders can also help their followers see the importance and value of their work. They can motivate employees to put the organization's interests ahead of theirs. Additionally, transformational leaders can help their followers to change their needs to higher-order concerns, such as the needs of the team or the community (Alessa, 2021; Dubinsky et al., 1995).

Research Questions

This main thrust of the study is to determine if the principal's leadership may have an influence on the teachers' performance in Liceo schools. Specifically, it will seek to answer the following questions:

1. What is the socio-demographic characteristics of the Liceo principals and teachers in Laguna in terms of:
 - 1.1. educational attainment; and
 - 1.2. years of service on current position?
2. What is the performance of the teachers in the 2023 Yearly Evaluation?
3. What is the assessment of the teacher on the principals' leadership style that influence the teachers' performance in terms of:
 - 3.1. transformational leadership; and
 - 3.2. transactional leadership?
4. Is there significant difference on the assessment of the principal's leadership style in each school?
5. Is there significant difference on the assessment of principal's leadership style based on the respondent's profile?
6. Is there a significant relationship between the leadership style of the principal and the teachers' performance?
7. What development plan of leadership style may be proposed to implement in Liceo schools?

Methodology

Research Design

This research utilized a quantitative research design. Quantitative research is a type of research that uses numbers to collect and analyze data. It can be used to find patterns and trends in data, make predictions about future outcomes, and test the relationships between different variables. Quantitative research is used to generalize results to a broader population, meaning that the findings of a study can be applied to people other than those who participated in the study (Bhandari, 2023).

This research was descriptive in nature. One kind of quantitative research used to precisely and methodically characterize a population, circumstance, or phenomena is called descriptive research. It can respond to inquiries about what, where, when, and how, but not why. It measures and observes variables without changing them through the use of several research techniques.

Respondents

The respondents of the study were teachers who are currently employed in each Liceo school of Cluster 2 namely; Liceo de San Pablo (23); Liceo de Calauan (9), Liceo de Pila (37), Liceo de Liliw (11), Liceo de Victoria (18), and ICCS Sta. Cruz (10). Among the 7 schools, there were only 6 schools that responded. Out of 278 respondents only 108 were collected from 6 schools that responded to the survey via online and printed.

This study utilized a non-probability purposive sampling technique. Frost (2023) defined this technique as a non-probability method for obtaining a sample where researchers use their expertise to choose specific participants to help the study meet its goals. These subjects have particular characteristics that the researchers need to evaluate their research question. Participants were chosen on purpose. This technique is most appropriate since the study focused on leadership style and teachers' performance in Liceo schools. The principal of Liceo leads the whole school community, including students, teachers, staff, parents, and community partners. They also manage the administration of all work related to students, teachers, and staff, making them the most suitable for gathering data for leadership style. Additionally, since the study focused on teachers' performance, it includes the teachers of Liceo Schools in Cluster 2.

Instrument

An adopted questionnaires from the study of Ramos (2021) and Jensen et. al (2019) were used in conducting and data gathering for this research study, which include the different indicators of the two-leadership style – transformational and transactional.

The research instrument consists of two parts. The first part of the instrument was the demographic profile of the respondents, and the second part contains the indicators of the two-leadership style – transformational and transactional leadership style.

Some of the respondents answered the questions through Google Forms. The questionnaires sought to determine if the principals' leadership have an influence toward the teachers' performance.

Procedure

The researcher asked to permission from the head office of the school system to conduct the study. The researcher sought permission

from the respondents, with approval from the head office and the Supervisor of Cluster 2. The data collected will be secured with utmost confidentiality.

An adapted questionnaire was distributed to the respondents online using Google Forms and through printed hand-outs of it. The researcher personally handed out the printed copies of the survey questionnaires from Liceo de Victoria to Liceo de Liliw school principals or the academic coordinator (if the school principal is not around).

The first part of the questionnaire consisted of questions that answered the basic data such as - name, years in service and the school where they are affiliated. The second part of the questionnaire is a 5-point Likert scale about the principals' leadership skills – transformational and transactional.

Data Analysis

For the analysis and interpretation of the gathered data in this study, the following treatment were used:

Frequency count and percentage were used to determine the socio-demographic characteristics of the Liceo principals and teachers in Laguna in terms of their educational attainment; and years of service on current position. The same treatment was used to determine the performance of the teachers in the 2023 Yearly Evaluation.

Mean and standard deviation were utilized to find out the assessment of the principal and teacher on the principals' leadership style that influence the teachers' performance in terms of Transformational Leadership and Transactional Leadership.

Kruskal-Wallis H test was used to determine if there exist significant difference on the assessment of the principal's leadership style in each school. The same treatment was also used to determine if there exist significant difference on the assessment of principal's leadership style based on the respondent's profile.

Spearman's Rank-Order Correlation was employed to find out if there is significant relationship between the leadership style of the principal and the teachers' performance.

Results and Discussion

This section presented the data analysis and results in a systematic structure corresponding to the research problems.

It highlights the study's findings, which support existing studies of transformational and transactional leadership styles.

Part I. Socio-demographic Profile of the Respondents

Table 1. Educational Attainment of Respondents

<i>Highest Educational Attainment</i>	<i>Frequency (f)</i>	<i>Percent (%)</i>
Bachelor's Degree	82	76
Master's Degree	7	6
With Master's Units	19	18
Total	108	100

The data presented in table 1 above showed the educational attainment of the respondents. Most respondents have Bachelor's degrees, occupying 76% of the total respondents, while only 6% have Master's degrees. It can be said that few teachers at Liceo Schools place importance on professional growth.

Vural and Basaran (2021), posited that teachers who earn Master's degrees aim to increase their knowledge in the field, conduct academic studies, specialize, do their profession better, or become academicians. It was also mentioned in the study of Genova et al. (2023) that earning a master's degree can also be one mechanism for teachers to develop their competence in the profession, as quality teachers are essential for sustainable nation-building.

Furthermore, Astuti et al. (2020), teachers are also required to enhance their knowledge and skills. Teachers should also improve their teaching styles, techniques, and cognitive aspects since the primary role of the teachers is to teach individuals. For this improvement to happen, learning should be continuous, not just for the students or learners, but for everyone, specifically those serving in the education sector.

Table 2. Years in Service on Current Position of Respondents

<i>Years in Service</i>	<i>Frequency (f)</i>	<i>Percent (%)</i>
1-3 years	26	24
4-6 years	21	19
7 years and above	34	31
Less than 1 year	27	25
Total	108	100

The data in table 2 presents the years in service of the employees in Liceo schools who participated in the study. Most of the respondents, approximately 31%, had already been employed in the institution for more than seven (7) years. Teachers in service for 4-6 years occupy the least portion of the respondents, only at 19%. In this data, most respondents have lasted more than 7 years in the institution because the school head acknowledges their efforts as teachers.

In the study of Chiong et al. (2017), some reasons that make an educator stay longer in an institution because of the current and future teachers' intrinsic motivation, meaning they find the process of teaching and their subject enjoyable, and altruistic motivations, that is finding teaching socially meaningful, are factors that make teachers enter their profession—in comparison with extrinsic reasons like holidays and pay.

Part II. Teachers Performance

Table 3. *SY 2022-2023 Yearly Evaluation of Teachers'*

<i>Interval</i>	<i>f</i>	<i>%</i>	<i>Interpretation</i>
95-100	34	31	Outstanding
90-94	61	56	Very Satisfactory
85-89	8	7	Satisfactory
80-84	4	4	Unsatisfactory
79 below	1	1	Poor
	108	100	

Legend: 4.21-5.00 Always; 3.14 – 4.20 Often; 2.61-3.40 Occasionally; 1.81 – 2.60 Rare; 1.00 1.80 Never

The data from table 3 showed the yearly teacher performance evaluation in Liceo schools. The data from Table 3 shows that out of 108 respondents, 56% of the teachers got 90-94 as their yearly evaluation, which is very satisfactory. This was followed by 31% of the respondents who got 95-100 and 1% who got 79 below as their evaluation. The teachers here assessed the students and their colleagues for 56% of the respondents who got very satisfactory yearly performance. From the data, it can reveal that almost 87% of the teachers performed according to the set performance standards.

Ozkan (2020), asserted that good teachers play a crucial role in making schools effective. It is tough to make schools work well, but if teachers are committed and do their best, it can happen. To deal with these challenges and meet the school's goals, teachers need to be actively involved and perform at their best. So, policymakers and school leaders should think about ways to help teachers assess their performance, get feedback, and set up systems to improve based on that feedback.

Part III.

Table 4. *Assessment of the Respondents on the Principals' Leadership Style that influence the teachers' performance*

<i>Indicator</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Std.</i>	<i>Remarks Deviation</i>
<i>Transformational Leadership Style</i>			
Intellectual Stimulation	4.14	0.67	Often
Individualized Consideration	4.16	0.73	Often
Inspirational Motivation	4.35	0.86	Always
Idealized Influence	4.33	0.67	Always
Overall	4.24	0.68	Always
<i>Transactional Leadership Style</i>			
Contingent Reward	4.07	0.84	Often
Active Management Exception	4.01	0.70	Often
Passive Management Exception	3.63	0.88	Often
Overall	3.90	0.72	Often

Legend: 4.21-5.00 Always; 3.14 – 4.20 Often; 2.61-3.40 Occasionally; 1.81 – 2.60 Rare; 1.00 - 1.80 Never

The data from Table 4 above displays the results of a survey conducted to assess the impact of principals' leadership styles on teachers' performance. The table presents different indicators of two leadership styles: transformational and transactional. The transformational leadership style has four indicators: Intellectual Stimulation, Individualized Consideration, Inspiration, and Influence.

The first indicator of transformation leadership style is intellectual stimulation, gathered 4.14 as the mean and 0.67 for its standard deviation. In this data, it only shows that this indicator is often seen in their principal. Following the individualized consideration, in the data presented above it has 4.16 as its mean and 0.73 standard deviation, the teachers of Liceo school often observe this indicator to their school leader. The third indicator is inspiration motivation, this indicator gained the highest mean and highest standard deviation. And last indicator, which is idealized influence, the data above present that it has a mean of 4.33 and a standard deviation of 0.67, this indicator of the transformational leadership style, is always observed by the Liceo school teachers in their school principal.

Among these indicators, Inspirational Motivation has the highest mean score which 4.35. Also, it shows that it has the highest standard deviation which is 0.86. This indicator refers to how transformational leaders energize and motivate their followers. A school head or

principal who possesses this indicator of transformational leadership has a clear vision of how they will lead their subordinates.

Chebon et al. (2019), Inspirational Motivation involves encouraging followers to raise their consciousness about and elicit their commitment to the mission and vision. This indicator of transformational leadership may increase teachers' performance. Chebon et al. (2019) also cite Krishnan (2000), who connects Inspirational Motivation with ethical notions, suggesting that leaders, when showing care for organizational vision and motivating the followers, become more prone to ethical decisions.

Next is the transactional leadership style. Harrison (2018) posited in Bass (1985) the indicators of transactional leadership style are the contingent reward, active management-by exemption, and passive management-by-exemption. Contingent rewards entail offering incentives to incentivize subordinates. Followers are informed about the performance standards expected of them and the rewards they stand to receive upon meeting these standards. Management by exception, originally introduced and later refined by Bass and Avolio (1990) in subsequent studies, can take an active or passive form. In its active manifestation, leaders actively monitor followers, seeking out errors and enforcing rules or taking coercive measures to discourage future mistakes.

The data presents that contingent reward occupies 4.07 as the highest mean among the three indicators of this leadership style. The data presented indicates that this indicator shows that teachers' performance is influenced if the school head or the principal gave rewards to those teachers who performed well and it will also influence other teachers to do well in their job.

As stated in the portfolio of Regina Burton that these rewards can be used and are used outside of the scope of the regular performance appraisal of the employee. When an employee does an exceptional job or goes above and beyond the scope of his or her job to help achieve a company goal then these employees should be rewarded with some type of contingent reward. The reward offered is the one that ought to be commensurate with the type of achievement the employee has mustered. Moreover, teachers will hence be motivated to place efforts in doing their job well for various good outputs and rewards. (Bass, 1985; Avolio et al., 1999; Goodwin et al., 2001; Bass et al., 2003; Wang et al., 2011, Xenikou, 2017).

Moreover, the data for table 4, shows that the among the seven indicators presented by the two leadership styles, it was found out that the highest standard deviation in the indicator of transactional leadership style which is active management by exception, which signifies the highest disposition among the responses. This shows that by adopting this indicator of the transactional leadership style, leaders can ensure that deviations are promptly addressed. Team members recognize the significance of their performance and understand that corrective measures will be implemented.

Part IV.

Table 5. *Test of Difference on the Assessment of the Principal's Leadership Style in each School*

Variable	<i>rs</i> value	<i>p</i> -value	Interpretation
Transformational Leadership Style	14.57	0.012	Significant
Transactional Leadership Style	5.27	0.384	Not Significant

Legend: < 0.05 Significant; ≥ 0.05 Not Significant

The data presented in table 5 above shows the results of a test of difference on the assessment of the principal's leadership style in each school. The data indicates that transformational leadership is significant to its assessment in each school. Teachers in Cluster 2 of Liceo schools observed that the leadership style of their principals does have differences. On the other hand, transactional leadership shows that there is no significant difference on the assessment of the principal's leadership style in each school.

Transformational leadership improved both individual and team performance, as stated by Derindag (2020) study. However, the impact on individual performance was more substantial when staff members had confidence in their manager. Team trust had a different impact. According to the study's findings, transformational leadership can successfully raise both team and individual performance, but subordinates must have the supervisor's trust. Employee motivation and engagement are higher amongst those who have faith in their manager. Improved performance is a possible outcome of transformational leadership for both individuals and teams.

Part V.

Table 6. *Test of Difference on the Assessment of the Principal's Leadership Style based on the Respondent's Profile*

Variable	<i>rs</i> value	<i>p</i> -value	Interpretation
Educational Attainment	1.70	0.428	Not Significant
Length of Service	5.05	0.167	Not Significant

Legend: < 0.05 Significant; ≥ 0.05 Not Significant

The data from Table 6, presented the result of the test of difference on the assessment of the principal's leadership style based on the respondent's profile was demonstrated. It shows no significant difference in the assessment as grouped according to educational attainment based on $H= 1.70$ and $p=0.428$. In the data presented, the educational attainment of the teachers in terms of length of service, it was also found that there is no significant difference in the assessment of the principal's leadership style based on $H= 5.05$ and $p=0.167$. It only showed that the respondent's profile – both educational attainment and length of service did not have any significant

effect on the leadership style of the principal in Liceo schools, particularly Cluster 2.

In this data, educational attainment shows that leadership effectiveness does not necessarily correspond directly with formal education. In simpler terms, having advanced degrees or specific qualifications may not automatically make someone a better leader. On the other hand, length of service, schools should recognize that effective leadership can be demonstrated by both experienced and relatively new school heads. Rather than assuming that longer tenure automatically leads to better leadership, institutions should assess leadership qualities, adaptability, and performance.

In contrast, the study of Alenazi et al. (2017), asserted that the respondent's profile had significant difference on the leadership style – transformational and transactional of a leader. It is also stated in their study that the educational attainment had the greatest influence on leadership behavior.

Part VI.

Table 7. *Test of Relationship between the Principal's Leadership Style and the Teachers' Performance*

Variable	<i>r</i> s value	<i>p</i> -value	Interpretation
Transformational	-.205	.033	Significant
Transactional	-.211	.028	Significant

Legend: < 0.05 Significant; ≥ 0.05 Not Significant

The data from table 7 above presents test of relationship between the principal's leadership style and the teachers' performance. It shows that both the leadership style – transformational and transactional have an influence on the performance of the teachers based on the p-value which .033 and .028 that signifies that both the leadership style is significant. The data presented that the principals' transformational and transactional leadership styles in Cluster 2 Liceo schools influence the teachers' performances.

According to Al-Amin's (2017) study, transformational leadership is positively associated with employee performance. Also, Al-Amin (2017) confirms that leadership behaviors affect employee performance, and transformational leaders produce positive behaviors that encourage employees to drive performance.

On the other hand, transactional leadership style shows that it has also a significant relationship towards teachers' performance. This leadership style had an influence towards teachers' performance in Liceo schools, since according to the study of Duraku and Hoxha (2021), as cited in Gilbert and Kelloway, (2018) that transactional leadership encompasses a broad spectrum of leadership styles, ranging from laissez-faire leadership (where the leader hardly responds in any situation) to active or passive management by exception (where the leader reacts only to negative or critique-worthy behaviors), and finally to providing rewards and punishment based on performance.

Purwanto, Bernarto, et al. (2020) found that both transformational and transactional leadership philosophies significantly and positively influence organizational performance. Other research by Tsai et al. (2015), Qijun et al. (2016), and Shih et al. (2012) also supports the notion that transactional and transformational leadership styles have an impact on performance.

Part VII. Development plan of leadership style may be proposed to implement in Liceo schools

This part of the chapter presents the proposed leadership style to be implemented in Liceo schools, particularly in Cluster 2. The data gathered in this study shows that inspirational motivation is the most seen indicator of the transformational leadership style. Moreover, as for the transactional leadership theory, among its indicators, contingent reward is the most seen in this leadership style. This development plan for leadership may be implemented so that teachers in Liceo school, particularly in Cluster 2, may increase their performance level.

The proposed development plan consists of the following: (1) Faculty Development where as it is for improving teacher's performance and developing a culture of professional development is provided by this strategy. It places a focus on teamwork, goal-setting, and continuous assistance; (2) Student Development, the goal is to increase students' achievement and learning in a variety of subjects. It emphasizes developing core skills, creating a friendly learning environment, and providing individualized instruction; and (3) Leadership Development is to strengthen leadership skills and effectiveness, foster improved team management, a positive organizational culture, and individual career growth. It is also to focus on the focal point on improving the overall performance of the institution.

Conclusions

Based on the findings of this study, the following conclusions were made:

In Liceo schools, the majority of teachers have more than seven years of experience. It is evident that the teaching staff has a considerable amount of expertise. This shows institutional knowledge and stability inside the school, which have a good effect on student outcomes, teacher quality, and the culture of the school as a whole. 56% of the teachers got very satisfactory yearly evaluation;

Both the educational attainment and length of service do not have significant difference on the leadership style of the principal;

As per the leadership styles, Inspirational motivation got the highest mean among the four indicators of Transformational leadership style; and Contingent reward for Transactional leadership style;

Transformational and transactional leadership styles have a significant relationship on the teacher's performance.

This section outlines a set of recommendations aimed at addressing key challenges and leveraging opportunities identified through this study. By providing clear guidance for stakeholders and decision-makers, these recommendations seek to foster positive change and promote the improvement of the performance of the teachers who are employed in a Catholic institution which is Liceo schools. Listed below are some of the recommendations:

In terms of the Transactional Leadership Style, each of the indicator should be utilized or should be seen by the employees or the teachers in order for them to do well in their responsibilities.

In Transactional Leadership Style, passive-management style got the least mean among the three indicators; for this to improve, leaders or principals should be consistent on giving sanctions regarding teachers who violate the school policies.

Liceo schools may establish mentorship programs where experienced teacher can mentor newer colleagues, showing their knowledge and expertise

References

- 7 Major Leadership Theories Every Manager Should Master in 2022. (2020, February 6). Simplilearn.Com. www.simplilearn.com/top-leadership-theories-every-manager-should-know-article
- Agustin, M., Hidayatulloh, H., & Muhammad, D. H. (2022, June 20). The Influence of Principal's Democratic Leadership Style on Teacher Performance. *KnE Social Sciences*, 400–408. <https://doi.org/10.18502/kss.v7i10.11242>
- Al-Malki, M., & Juan, W. (2018). Leadership Styles and Job Performance: A Literature Review. *Journal of International Business Research and Marketing*, 3(3), 40–49. <https://doi.org/10.18775/jibrm.1849-8558.2015.33.3004>
- Al-Mansoori, R. S., & Koç, M. (2019). Transformational leadership, systems, and intrinsic motivation impacts on innovation in higher education institutes: Faculty perspectives in engineering colleges. *Sustainability*, 11(15), 4072. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su11154072>
- Al-Amin, M. (2017). Transformational leadership and employee performance: Mediating effect of employee engagement. *ResearchGate*. <https://www.researchgate.net/publication/328530143>
- Alenazi, F., Muenjohn, N., & McMurray, A. (2017). The effect of demographic characteristics on leadership behaviour. *World Journal of Management*, 8(1), 15–31. <https://doi.org/10.21102/wjm.2017.03.81.02>
- Alessa, G. S. (2021). The dimensions of transformational leadership and its organizational effects in public universities in Saudi Arabia: A systematic review. *Frontiers in Psychology*, 12. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2021.682092>
- Ariawan, A. (2020). Transformational and transactional leadership improve performance: Evidence from lecture faculty of economics, University of Ichsan Gorontalo. *Ichsan University*. <https://www.academia.edu/41820431>
- Asnawati, Arafat, Y., & Putra, A. Y. (2021). The effect of supervision and work motivation of school principal on the performance of elementary school teachers. *Proceedings of the International Conference on Education Universitas PGRI Palembang (INCoEPP 2021)*. <https://doi.org/10.2991/assehr.k.210716.051>
- Austuti, R. W., Fitria, H., & Rohana, R. (2020). The influence of leadership styles and work motivation on teacher's performance. *Journal of Social Work and Science Education*, 1(2), 105–114. <https://doi.org/10.52690/jswse.v1i2.33>
- Bakker, A. B., Hetland, J., Olsen, O. K., & Espevik, R. (2023). Daily transformational leadership: A source of inspiration for follower performance? *European Management Journal*, 41(5), 700–708. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.emj.2022.04.004>
- Betz, M. B. (2021, August 6). Transactional leadership style: pros, cons, and examples. *BetterUp*. <https://www.betterup.com/blog/transactional-leadership>
- Bhandari, P. (2023). Correlational research | When & how to use. *Scribbr*. <https://www.scribbr.com/methodology/correlational-research/>
- Bhandari, P. (2023). What is quantitative research? | Definition, uses & methods. *Scribbr*. <https://www.scribbr.com/methodology/quantitative-research/>
- Buenvinida, L. P., & Ramos, M. T. S. (2019). Transformational leadership practices of school heads and performance of city schools in the Division of First District of Laguna, Philippines. *People: International Journal of Social Sciences*, 4(3), 799–812. <https://doi.org/10.20319/pijss.2019.43.799812>
- Chebon, S. K., Aruasa, W., & Chirchir, L. K. (2019). Effect of inspirational motivation and idealized influence on employee

- performance at Moi Teaching and Referral Hospital, Eldoret, Kenya. *International Journal of Business and Social Science*, 10(7). <https://doi.org/10.30845/ijbss.v10n7p14>
- Chiong, C., Menzies, L., & Parameshwaran, M. (2017). Why do long-serving teachers stay in the teaching profession? Analysing the motivations of teachers with 10 or more years' experience in England. *British Educational Research Journal*, 43(6), 1083–1110. <https://doi.org/10.1002/berj.3302>
- Davis, A. T. D. (2023, July). Transformational leadership: Exploring its impact on job satisfaction, job performance, and employee empowerment. ProQuest. <https://search.proquest.com/openview/b1ce8d70a7cc347480c45d80d65142f0>
- Demirtas, O. D., & Karaca, M. K. (n.d.). *A Handbook of Leadership Styles*. Retrieved September 29, 2022. <https://www.cambridgescholars.com/resources/pdfs/978-1-5275-4598-4-sample.pdf>
- Duraku, H. Z., & Hoxha, L. (2021). Impact of transformational and transactional attributes of school principal leadership on teachers' motivation for work. *Frontiers in Education*, 6, 659919. <https://doi.org/10.3389/educ.2021.659919>
- Evangelio, M. C. E. (2019). *A Reflective Training Guide for School Principals on Responsive Leadership in the 21st Century* [Dissertation].
- Gentova, C. S. G., Madrigal, D. V. M., & Bual, J. M. B. (2023). A tracer study of graduates of education graduate programs 2018-2022 of the University of Negros Occidental-Recoletos Graduate School. *Technium Social Sciences Journal*, 47, 77–101. <https://philarchive.org/archive/GENATS-2>
- Handoko, A. (2015). The effect of transformational leadership and work motivation on employee performance with job satisfaction as intervening variables. Faculty of Economics and Business, Diponegoro University, Semarang.
- Harapan, E., Wardiah, D., & Nuryani, N. (2021). Principal's managerial role in improving the quality of education in the primary school. *Journal of Social Work and Science Education*, 2(1), 52-59. <https://doi.org/10.52690/jswse.v2i1.205>
- Harrison, C. (2018). *Leadership Theory and Research*. Springer eBooks. <https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-319-68672-1>
- Indrawan, I., Evanirosa, Ali, R., Ramadan, Hanif, M., Harun, I., Hanum, L., Purwanto, A. et al. (2020). Develop model of transactional, transformational, democratic and autocratic leadership style for Indonesian school performance in education 4.0 era. *Systematic Reviews in Pharmacy*, 11(9), 409–419. <https://doi.org/10.31838/srp.2020.9.58>
- Jamon, B. E. (2017). School administrators' leadership styles, attributes and functions towards education-progression driven era. *Academia.edu*. https://www.academia.edu/32468973/SCHOOL_ADMINISTRATORS_LEADERSHIP_STYLES_ATTRIBUTES_AND_FUNCTIONS_TOWARDS_EDUCATION_PROGRESSION_DRIVEN_ERA
- Jensen, U. T., Andersen, L. B., Bro, L. L., Bøllingtoft, A., Eriksen, T. L. M., Holten, A. L., & Würtz, A. (2019). Conceptualizing and measuring transformational and transactional leadership. *Administration & Society*, 51(1), 3–33. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0095399716667157>
- Kalsoom, Z., Khan, M. A., & Zubair, S. S. (2018). Impact of transactional leadership and transformational leadership on employee performance: A case of FMCG industry of Pakistan. *Industrial Engineering Letters*, 8(3), 23–30. <https://www.iiste.org/Journals/index.php/IEL/article/download/42795/44089>
- Kartini, D., Kristiawan, M., & Fitria, H. (2020). The influence of principal's leadership, academic supervision, and professional competence toward teachers' performance. *International Journal of Progressive Sciences and Technologies*, 20(1), 156–164. <https://doi.org/10.52155/ijpsat.v20.1.1730>
- Korejan, M. M. M. M., & Shahbazi, H. (2016). An analysis of the transformational leadership theory. *Journal of Fundamental and Applied Sciences*, 8(3), 452. <https://doi.org/10.4314/jfas.v8i3s.192>
- Lindberg, C. (2022, August 18). Transactional leadership – explained by a CEO. *Leadership Ahoy!* <https://www.leadershipahoy.com/transactional-leadership-what-is-it-pros-cons-examples>
- Lindberg, C. (2022, August 24). Transactional leadership: Active management by exception. *Leadership Ahoy!* <https://www.leadershipahoy.com/transactional-leadership-active-management-by-exception>
- Lindberg, C. (2022, August 18). Transactional leadership: Contingent reward. *Leadership Ahoy!* <https://www.leadershipahoy.com/transactional-leadership-contingent-reward>
- May, L. F., Abdurrahman, A., Hariri, H., Sowiyah, S., & Rahman, B. (2020). The influence of principal managerial competence on teacher performance at schools in Bandar Lampung. *Tadris: Jurnal Keguruan Dan Ilmu Tarbiyah*, 5(1), 121–130. <https://doi.org/10.24042/tadris.v5i1.5391>

Novitasari, D., Supiana, N., Supriatna, H., Fikri, M. A. A., & Asbari, M. (2021). The role of leadership in innovation performance: Transactional versus transformational style. *JIMFE (Jurnal Ilmiah Manajemen Fakultas Ekonomi)*. <https://doi.org/10.34203/jimfe.v7i1.2981>

Özkan, P. (2020). The role of teacher performance in school effectiveness. *Iszu*. https://www.academia.edu/42064465/The_Role_of_Teacher_Performance_in_School_Effectiveness

Principal. (2024). In Merriam-Webster Dictionary. <https://www.merriam-webster.com/dictionary/principal>

Putra, A. S., Waruwu, H., Asbari, M., Novitasari, D., & Purwanto, A. (2020). Leadership in the innovation era: Transactional or transformational style? *International Journal of Social and Management Studies (IJOSMAS)*, 1(1), 89–94. <https://doi.org/10.5555/ijosmas.v1i1.10>

Purwanto, A., Kusumaningsih, S. W., & Prasetya, A. B. (2020). Did transformational leadership elitist and antidemocratic? A literature review. *International Journal of Social, Policy and Law (IJOSPL)*, 1(1), 1–11. <https://doi.org/10.8888/ijospl.v1i1.1>

Purwanto, A., Mufid, A., & AS, W. (2020). The influence of transformational leadership, job satisfaction and organizational citizenship behavior on. *ResearchGate*. https://www.researchgate.net/publication/344550269_The_Influence_of_Transformational_Leadership_Job_Satisfaction_and_Organizational_Citizenship_Behavior_on_the_Performance_of_Islamic_School_Teachers

Purwanto, A., Bernarto, I., Asbari, M., Wijayanti, L. M., & Hyun, C. C. (2020). Effect of transformational and transactional leadership style on public health centre performance. *Journal of Research in Business, Economics, and Education*, 2(1), 304–314. <https://e-journal.stie-kusumanegara.ac.id/index.php/jrbee/article/view/33>

Rachmawati, Y., & Suyatno, S. (2021). The effect of principals' competencies on teachers' job satisfaction and work commitment. *Participatory Educational Research*, 8(1), 362-378. <https://doi.org/10.17275/per.21.21.8.1>

Rahmawati, Y. (2022). Transformational and instructional leadership styles to improve teacher performance: Literature review. *International Journal of Current Science Research and Review*, 5(7). <https://doi.org/10.47191/ijcsrr/v5-i7-61>

Ramli et al. (2019, December). The role of transactional leadership towards organizational commitment. *International Journal of Business, Economics and Law*, 20(5), 20(2289–1552). https://ijbel.com/wp-content/uploads/2020/01/IJBEL20_222.pdf

Ramos, L. E. (2021). Transformational leadership and school-based management: Inputs to an effective school governance [MA Thesis].

Raupu, S., Maharani, D., Mahmud, H., & Alauddin, A. (2021). Democratic leadership and its impact on teacher performance. *Al-Ishlah*, 13(3), 1556–1570. <https://doi.org/10.35445/alishlah.v13i3.990>

Renjith, V., G, R., & George, A. (2015). Transformational leadership in nursing. *ResearchGate*. https://www.researchgate.net/publication/277138454_TRANSFORMATIONAL_LEADERSHIP_IN_NURSING

Saleem, A., Aslam, S., Yin, H. B., & Rao, C. (2020, April 21). Principal leadership styles and teacher job performance: Viewpoint of middle management. *Sustainability*, 12(8), 3390. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su12083390>

Sherwani, K. H., Bala, H., & Khatoon, G. (2023). Perceived organizational support and employee loyalty as mediators in the relationship between leadership effectiveness and task performance: A study of nurses in Erbil City. *Research Square*. <https://doi.org/10.21203/rs.3.rs-3436512/v1>

Sparks, J. S. (2021). Understanding transformational leadership during a time of uncertainty. *Alabama Journal of Educational Leadership*, 8, 10–15. <https://eric.ed.gov/?q=leadership&pg=6&id=EJ1322100>

Steenkamp, I. (2021). Critically assessing how transactional and transformational leadership affects workforce behaviour. *Unicaf*. https://www.academia.edu/50807718/Critically_assessing_how_Transactional_and_Transformational_Leadership_affects_workforce_behaviour

Sunaryo, W. et al. (2021, January 1). Develop model of transformational, transactional leadership style, teachers perception and teachers satisfaction: Evidence from Indonesian high schools. *Psychology and Education Journal*, 58(1), 2305–2319. <https://doi.org/10.17762/pae.v58i1.1107>

Suratman, S., Arafat, Y., & Eddy, S. (2020). The influence of principal's leadership and teacher's competence toward teacher's performance in Indonesia. *Journal of Social Work and Science Education*, 1(2), 96-104. <https://doi.org/10.52690/jswse.v1i2.32>

Team, C. (2023, January 16). Transformational leadership. *Corporate Finance Institute*. <https://corporatefinanceinstitute.com/resources/management/transformational-leadership/>

Teacher. (n.d.). *Oxford Advanced Learner's Dictionary*. <https://www.oxfordlearnersdictionaries.com/definition/english/teacher>

Umar, O. S., Hoque, K. E., & Kenayathulla, H. B. (2021). Principal leadership practices and school effectiveness in Niger State, Nigeria. *South African Journal of Education*, 41(3). <https://doi.org/10.15700/saje.v41n3a1859>

Ugochukwu, C. (2024, July 10). Transformational leadership style: How to inspire and motivate. *Simply Psychology*. <https://www.simplypsychology.org/what-is-transformational-leadership.html>

Views on contingent reward systems. (n.d.). Regina Burton Career Portfolio. <https://sites.psu.edu/reginaburtonhcareerportfolio/examples-of-work/views-on-contingent-reward-systems/>

Vural, Ö. F., & Başaran, M. (2021). The reasons for teachers' preference for master's degree. *ResearchGate*. https://www.researchgate.net/publication/348154619_The_reasons_for_teachers'_preference_for_Master's_degree

Wang, H., & Guan, B. (2018). The positive effect of authoritarian leadership on employee performance: The moderating role of power distance. *Frontiers in Psychology*, 9. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2018.00357>

Xenikou, A. (2017). Transformational leadership, transactional contingent reward, and organizational identification: The mediating effect of perceived innovation and goal culture orientations. *Frontiers in Psychology*, 8. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2017.01754>

Affiliations and Corresponding Information

Norlyn S. Letegio

Liceo De San Pablo – Philippines

Elmer C. Escala

Col. Lauro Dizon Memorial Integrated High School

Department of Education – Philippines